

Is A Standard Definition of Corporate Social Responsibility Necessary for Its Legal Enforcement in Tanzania?

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Abstract:

Despite growing awareness of corporate social responsibility (CSR), there is no consensus on its definition. This paper investigates whether a standardised definition of CSR is necessary for its legal enforcement in Tanzania. The paper employed doctrinal legal research to examine the CSR legal framework and identify challenges that a standardised definition of CSR can resolve. The findings highlight that while the meaning of CSR is not in dispute, the definition of CSR remains a subject of debate, ultimately contributing to poor CSR practices in Tanzania. Moreover, the existing CSR legal framework in Tanzania has significant challenges, and having a standardised definition is a key step towards addressing them. Although the paper finds that a standardised definition of CSR is not a complete panacea for challenges in performing CSR obligations, it does contribute to implementing CSR goals.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, Standard Definition, Legal Enforcement, Tanzania.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) requires companies to operate in an ethical and sustainable manner.¹ Companies ought to take responsibility for the impacts of their activities on society and the environment.² CSR has a crucial role in ensuring the world achieves sustainable development. First, it encourages firms to reduce their carbon footprints, conserve natural resources, and invest in cleaner energy sources.³ Additionally, CSR requires businesses to promote fair labour practices, engage with relevant stakeholders, and consider community development, particularly in their operating areas.⁴ Moreover, enterprises must ensure their operations are transparent, ethical and accountable for their adverse impacts.⁵ Therefore, CSR mandates companies to manage not only for profit-making but also to contribute to sustainable and inclusive development by integrating social and environmental concerns into a company's operations.

Traditionally, CSR enforcement has been voluntary. Companies exercise their freedom and discretion in CSR initiatives based on the categories and scale of the undertakings.⁶ CSR voluntary enforcement has provided flexibility and innovation for CSR programs, influenced by factors such as enterprise size and industry operations.⁷ The CSR voluntary enforcement faced a lack of accountability.⁸ It also brought inconsistent implementation.⁹ The inconsistencies stem from companies' freedom to engage in CSR activities. Through voluntary enforcement, CSR benefits often fail to reach the intended communities.¹⁰ A

¹ R Steele, and S General, 'Guidance on social responsibility.' International standard ISO, 26000. (2010).

² N Juarsa and Y Persian, 'Corporate Social Responsibility in International Economic Law Perspective' (2016) 2(2) Brawijaya LJ 165 <https://doi.org/10.21776/ub.blj.2016.002.02.05> accessed 19th March 2025.

³ AFLAC, '2019 Aflac CSR Survey: Consumers, Investors Hold Corporations' Feet to the Fire (2019) <https://www.aflac.com/docs/about-aflac/csr-survey-assets/2019-aflac-csr-infographic-and-survey.pdf> accessed 9th December 2024.

⁴ S R Barakat, et al., 'The Influence of Corporate Social Responsibility on Employee Satisfaction' (2016) *Management Decision* 54(9), 2325–2339.

⁵ M Donia, et al., 'The Theorized Relationship between Organizational (Non)Compliance with the United Nations Guiding Principles on Human Rights and Desired Employee Workplace Outcomes' (2020) 12(5) *Sustainability* 2130.

⁶ CC Ekeolisa, 'Framework for Obligations Regarding Environmental and Human Rights Protection in Nigeria's Bilateral Investment Treaties' (2020) <https://core.ac.uk/download/304170220.pdf> accessed 19th March 2025.

⁷ D Ortiz-Avram and others, 'Exploring the Integration of Corporate Social Responsibility into the Strategies of Small-and Medium-Sized Enterprises: A Systematic Literature Review' (2018) 201 *Journal of Cleaner Production* 254

⁸ P M Manyanki and E M Msoka, 'Human Rights and Environmental Justice in Tanzania: Legal Responses to Mining and Land Disputes' (2025) 9(2) *Journal of African Interdisciplinary Studies* 88-103.

⁹ S K Mbirigenda and C T Msoka, 'Community Development Through Corporate Social Responsibility: Some Issues from Selected Companies in Tanzania' (2015) 6(1) *Syllabus Review* 99-125.

¹⁰ L L Melyoki, 'Corporate Social Responsibility Practices in the Extractive Sector in Tanzania: Is It a Transition from a Voluntary to Legislative Approach?' (2020) *Social Entrepreneurship and Corporate Social Responsibility* 423–437.

movement emerged to mandate CSR obligations through legislative enactments, addressing the gaps and limitations of voluntary enforcement.¹¹

Later, CSR legal enforcement was a solution to address the shortcomings of voluntary enforcement.¹² 'CSR legal enforcement' refers to using laws, regulations, and legal mechanisms by governments or regulatory bodies to mandate, monitor, and enforce companies' CSR obligations. Mauritius established mandatory corporate philanthropy in 2009, requiring companies to allocate a percentage of profits to CSR.¹³ Similarly, India mandates certain companies to allocate at least 2% of their average net profits over the previous three years to CSR undertakings, per the Companies Act of 2013.¹⁴ The UK has the Modern Slavery Act of 2015, requiring companies above an inevitable turnover to publish an annual statement detailing measures taken to prevent slavery and human trafficking in their supply chains.¹⁵ Additionally, large companies in France are required to create and disclose a vigilance plan under the Duty of Vigilance Law of 2017. This law aims to identify and prevent severe human rights violations and environmental damage resulting from their operations.¹⁶

Tanzania has laws that mandate companies to engage in CSR activities in the extractive sector. The laws include the Tanzania Extractive Industries (Transparency and Accountability) Act¹⁷, the Mining Act¹⁸, the Petroleum Act¹⁹, and the Mining (Corporate Social Responsibility) Regulations.²⁰ In other sectors, such as agriculture, finance, labour, and tourism, no single comprehensive legislation specifically addresses CSR, unlike in the extractive sectors. However, some general laws implicitly address certain CSR-related obligations. The Companies Act requires company directors to consider the interests of both employees and members.²¹ The Fair Competition Act²² prohibits misleading or deceptive trading conduct as part of consumer protection. The CSR mandatory laws establish legal and enforceable obligations such as CSR plan preparation, CSR spending,

¹¹ B Sheehy et al., 'Shifting from Soft to Hard Law: Motivating Compliance When Enacting Mandatory Corporate Social Responsibility' (2023) 24(4) European Business Organization Law Review 693

¹² Li-Wen Lin, 'Mandatory Corporate Social Responsibility Legislation Around the World: Emergent Varieties and National Experiences' (Oxford Business Law Blog, 10th November 2020) <https://blogs.law.ox.ac.uk/business-law-blog/blog/2020/11/mandatory-corporate-social-responsibility-legislation-around-world> accessed 27th March 2025.

¹³ R Pillay, *The Changing Nature of Corporate Social Responsibility: CSR and Development – The Case of Mauritius* (Routledge 2015).

¹⁴ Section 135 of Companies Act 2013.

¹⁵ Section 54 of the Modern Slavery Act of 2015.

¹⁶ A Schilling-Vacaflor, 'Putting the French Duty of Vigilance Law in Context: Towards Corporate Accountability for Human Rights Violations in the Global South?' (2021) 22 Hum Rights Rev 109.

¹⁷ The Tanzania Extractive Industries (Transparency and Accountability) Act, sections 15 and 16

¹⁸ The Mining Act, s 105

¹⁹ The Petroleum Act, s 222.

²⁰ G.N. No. 409 of 2023.

²¹ The Companies Act, s 183.

²² The Fair Competition Act, s 15.

and CSR reporting.²³ They also develop enforcement mechanisms, such as imposing penalties or fines for non-compliance with legal obligations and seeking damages for human rights violations resulting from the company's operations. Moreover, mandatory CSR laws aim to establish a standard for CSR across industries and regions.

Over the past decade, Tanzania has witnessed significant CSR awareness and practice growth.²⁴ The demands of international and domestic stakeholders have driven this growth.²⁵ However, the prevalent sectors include mining²⁶, manufacturing²⁷, banking²⁸, tourism²⁹, and telecommunications.³⁰ Community welfare has been the dominant focus of most CSR projects in Tanzania. Notably, CSR endeavours in education, health, environmental conservation, and infrastructure development are common in the country.³¹ Therefore, the extent and manner in which businesses from different sectors have undertaken CSR initiatives are significant enough to attract research and regulatory interests in Tanzania. However, current CSR practices neglect certain aspects, such as clean water and sanitation access.³² This neglect is due to the high costs that businesses may incur in such elements.³³ Moreover, CSR practices are not effective. Studies reveal misuse and malpractice³⁴, inconsistent practices³⁵, gaps between CSR commitment and implementation³⁶, misalignment of CSR projects and stakeholders' needs and interests in

²³ L W, Lin, 'Mandatory Corporate Social Responsibility Legislation Around the World: Emergent Varieties and National Experiences' (2020) 23 U Pa J Bus L 429

²⁴ W Maliganya and G Bulengela, 'Rethinking the Practices of Corporate Social Responsibility in the Mining Sector for Sustainable Development in Tanzania' (2025) 15(1) Journal of Management and Science 102-114.

²⁵ S E Fulgence, 'Corporate Social Responsibility in Tanzania' in Stephen Vertigans, Samuel O Idowu and René Schmidpeter (eds), *Corporate Social Responsibility in Sub-Saharan Africa* (CSR, Sustainability, Ethics & Governance, Springer 2016) 111-152.

²⁶ P M Manyanki and E M Msoka, 'Human Rights and Environmental Justice in Tanzania: Legal Responses to Mining and Land Disputes' (2025) 9(2) Journal of African Interdisciplinary Studies 88-103.

²⁷ E L Mwansasu and L R Mwangike, 'Environmental Sustainability Practices in Supply Chains and Manufacturing Firms' Performance: Evidence from Tanzania Breweries Limited' (2025) 8(1) SEISENSE Journal of Management 1-16.

²⁸ Q Mawinda and O Swalehe, 'Impact of CSR Practices on Bank Financial Performance: The Case of NMB Bank, Tanzania' (2024) 23(3) IUP Journal of Bank Management 52-71.

²⁹ S J Suluo, L Mossberg, T D Andersson, W Anderson and M J Assad, 'Corporate Sustainability Practices in Tourism—Evidence from Tanzania' (2023) 20(5) Tourism Planning & Development 747-768.

³⁰ H A Rugeiyamu, *The Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility on Financial Performance of the Telecom Companies: Case Study of TIGO Tanzania* (PhD thesis, The Open University of Tanzania 2020).

³¹ S K Mbirigenda and C T Msoka, 'Community Development Through Corporate Social Responsibility: Some Issues from Selected Companies in Tanzania' (2015) 6(1) Syllabus Review 99-125.

³² I O Gillo *et al.*, 'Barriers to Corporate Social Responsibility Implementation in Tanzania: Evidence from the North Mara Gold Mine' (2024) 14(2) African Journal of Development Studies.

³³ *Ibid*

³⁴ S Mbirigenda, *Corporate social responsibility in Tanzania: experience of misconception, misuse and malpractices in Contemporary Concerns in Development Studies: Perspectives from Tanzania and Zambia* (2015) 100.

³⁵ F M Philip, *Regulation of Corporate Social Responsibility Practices in Tanzania* (Master's Degree Dissertation, The Open University of Tanzania 2019).

³⁶ S K Mbirigenda, *Corporate Social Responsibility Management Systems in Tanzania: Opportunities, Challenges and Prospects for Local Communities' Participation in the Decision-Making Processes* (PhD

CSR practices.³⁷ Therefore, despite the growth of CSR, stakeholders face challenges in developing, deciding, implementing, and evaluating CSR plans and projects.

While the studies reveal challenges facing CSR enforcement despite the existing legal frameworks in Tanzania³⁸, a study investigating the relationship between the lack of a standardised CSR definition and the challenges facing CSR legal enforcement is missing. Hence, no previous research has examined whether a standardised CSR definition can address existing gaps and limitations in CSR legal enforcement. Therefore, this paper establishes a link between the lack of a standardised CSR definition and CSR legal enforcement. This paper explores how the absence of a common CSR understanding affects CSR legal enforcement in the country and determines whether a standardised CSR definition is the key to effective CSR legal enforcement. On the other hand, this paper contributes to the advancement of CSR scholarship by providing a comprehensive overview of CSR definitions and their impact on CSR legal enforcement, thereby enhancing the understanding of CSR's role in promoting sustainable and inclusive development. Similarly, this paper addresses the challenges and offers practical recommendations for effective CSR legal enforcement.

2. REVIEW OF RELEVANT LITERATURE

This section reviews relevant literature on the concept and enforcement of CSR. The essence is to establish how far previous studies have addressed the standard definition of CSR and its legal enforcement.

2.1 Conceptual Review

CSR is multifaceted because it encompasses various social, environmental, and ethical issues. CSR's various aspects reflect the complex interplay between businesses and society. The essence is that responsible corporate behaviour requires a holistic approach. Therefore, CSR involves integrating stakeholders' social, economic, environmental, and cultural priorities into business operations.³⁹ Carrol Pyramid Model of CSR suggests that businesses have four levels of responsibility, which build upon each other like a

thesis, University of Dar es Salaam 2015) <http://localhost:8080/xmlui/handle/123456789/3380> accessed on 2nd April 2025

³⁷ D Jamali and C Karam, 'Corporate Social Responsibility in Developing Countries as an Emerging Field of Study' (2018) 20(1) *International Journal of Management Reviews* 32-61. See also, A Chauhan, 'The Positive Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility: A Study of CSR in India' (2020) 11 *Indian Journal of Positive Psychology* 237.

³⁸ I O Gillo *et al.*, 'Barriers to Corporate Social Responsibility Implementation in Tanzania: Evidence from the North Mara Gold Mine' (2024) 14(2) *African Journal of Development Studies*. See W Maliganya *et al.*, 'Corporate Social Responsibility and the Challenges of the Regulatory Environment in the Tanzanian Mining Sector' in *Corporate Social Responsibility in Developing Countries: Challenges in the Extractive Industry* (Springer International Publishing 2023) 157-173.

³⁹ The Mining Act, s 105(2).

pyramid.⁴⁰ First is economic responsibility. It implies that companies must be profitable to survive. Hence, companies should provide goods and services that society needs while ensuring financial stability.⁴¹ Second is the legal responsibility. Legally, companies are required to comply with laws and regulations established by governments. Labour laws, environmental regulations, and fair trade constitute legal responsibilities. Third is ethical responsibility. Companies should go beyond legal requirements and act morally correctly. Ethically, companies must afford fair treatment to employees, ensuring ethical sourcing and maintaining honest business practices. Fourth is philanthropic responsibility. Companies should voluntarily give back to society through donations, community programs, and social initiatives. Hence, companies help communities without expecting direct financial returns.

The CSR concept is dynamic. In the early 20th century, CSR was a philanthropic act often separate from core business operations; companies engaged in CSR activities as benevolent activities. The early understanding of CSR centred on giving back to society.⁴² Hence, companies ought to share their success by supporting social causes. As societal awareness of labour abuses and environmental damage grew in the 20th century, CSR began to encompass ethical labour practices and environmental stewardship, laying the groundwork for understanding CSR as encompassing ethical and environmental obligations.⁴³ CSR was corporate citizenship.⁴⁴ Hence, companies, like individuals, are members of society and have ethical obligations that extend beyond profit-making.⁴⁵ Thus, companies should seek profit and aim to create value for society. In the 21st century, CSR is grounded in shared values that benefit humanity and the environment.⁴⁶ CSR is about balancing the profits companies receive with their impacts on people and the environment. The basis is the triple-bottom-line approach. Companies must develop coherent CSR strategies to maximise their positive impact on the social and environmental systems they operate.⁴⁷ Therefore, companies must design their products, services, and operations to address social and environmental concerns.

⁴⁰ A B Carroll, 'Carroll's Pyramid of CSR: Taking Another Look' (2016) 1 *Intl J of Corporate Social Responsibility* 1.

⁴¹ D Baden, 'A Reconstruction of Carroll's Pyramid of Corporate Social Responsibility for the 21st Century' (2016) 1(1) *International Journal of Corporate Social Responsibility* 8.

⁴² H J Shaw, 'The Role of CSR in Re-Empowering Local Communities' (2007) 3 *Social Responsibility J* 11.

⁴³ S Mackey, 'Virtue Ethics, CSR and "Corporate Citizenship"' (2014) 18 *J of Communication Management* 131.

⁴⁴ A J G Sison, 'From CSR to Corporate Citizenship: Anglo-American and Continental European Perspectives' (2009) 89 *J of Business Ethics* 235.

⁴⁵ D Matten, et al., 'Behind the Mask: Revealing the True Face of Corporate Citizenship' (2003) 45 *J of Business Ethics* 109.

⁴⁶ P S Menghwar and A Daood, 'Creating Shared Value: A Systematic Review, Synthesis and Integrative Perspective' (2021) 23 *Intl J of Mgmt Reviews* 466.

⁴⁷ A Żak, 'Triple Bottom Line Concept in Theory and Practice' (2015) 387(1) *Social Responsibility of Organizations: Directions of Changes* 251.

2.2 Empirical Review

Research indicates a notable increase in CSR awareness and implementation over the past decade.⁴⁸ The demands of international and domestic stakeholders have driven this growth.⁴⁹ However, the prevalent sectors include mining⁵⁰, manufacturing⁵¹, banking⁵², tourism⁵³, and telecommunications.⁵⁴ Community welfare has been the dominant focus of most CSR projects in Tanzania. Notably, CSR endeavours in education, health, environmental conservation, and infrastructure development are common in the country.⁵⁵ Therefore, the extent and manner in which businesses from different sectors have undertaken CSR initiatives are significant enough to attract research and regulatory interests in Tanzania.

Nevertheless, current CSR practices neglect certain aspects, such as clean water and sanitation access.⁵⁶ This neglect is due to the high costs that businesses may incur in such elements.⁵⁷ Moreover, CSR practices are not effective. Studies reveal misuse and malpractice⁵⁸, inconsistent practices⁵⁹, gaps between CSR commitment and implementation⁶⁰, misalignment of CSR projects and stakeholders' needs and interests in

⁴⁸ W Maliganya and G Bulengela, 'Rethinking the Practices of Corporate Social Responsibility in the Mining Sector for Sustainable Development in Tanzania' (2025) 15(1) *Journal of Management and Science* 102-114.

⁴⁹ S E Fulgence, 'Corporate Social Responsibility in Tanzania' in Stephen Vertigans, Samuel O Idowu and René Schmidpeter (eds), *Corporate Social Responsibility in Sub-Saharan Africa* (CSR, Sustainability, Ethics & Governance, Springer 2016) 111-152.

⁵⁰ P M Manyanki and E M Msoka, 'Human Rights and Environmental Justice in Tanzania: Legal Responses to Mining and Land Disputes' (2025) 9(2) *Journal of African Interdisciplinary Studies* 88-103.

⁵¹ E L Mwansasu and L R Mwangike, 'Environmental Sustainability Practices in Supply Chains and Manufacturing Firms' Performance: Evidence from Tanzania Breweries Limited' (2025) 8(1) *SEISENSE Journal of Management* 1-16.

⁵² Q Mawinda and O Swalehe, 'Impact of CSR Practices on Bank Financial Performance: The Case of NMB Bank, Tanzania' (2024) 23(3) *IUP Journal of Bank Management* 52-71.

⁵³ S J Suluo, L Mossberg, T D Andersson, W Anderson and M J Assad, 'Corporate Sustainability Practices in Tourism—Evidence from Tanzania' (2023) 20(5) *Tourism Planning & Development* 747-768.

⁵⁴ H A Rugeiyamu, *The Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility on Financial Performance of the Telecom Companies: Case Study of TIGO Tanzania* (PhD thesis, The Open University of Tanzania 2020).

⁵⁵ S K Mbirigenda and C T Msoka, 'Community Development Through Corporate Social Responsibility: Some Issues from Selected Companies in Tanzania' (2015) 6(1) *Syllabus Review* 99-125.

⁵⁶ I O Gillo *et al.*, 'Barriers to Corporate Social Responsibility Implementation in Tanzania: Evidence from the North Mara Gold Mine' (2024) 14(2) *African Journal of Development Studies*.

⁵⁷ *Ibid*

⁵⁸ S Mbirigenda, *Corporate social responsibility in Tanzania: experience of misconception, misuse and malpractices in Contemporary Concerns in Development Studies: Perspectives from Tanzania and Zambia* (2015) 100.

⁵⁹ F M Philip, *Regulation of Corporate Social Responsibility Practices in Tanzania* (Master's Degree Dissertation, The Open University of Tanzania 2019).

⁶⁰ S K Mbirigenda, *Corporate Social Responsibility Management Systems in Tanzania: Opportunities, Challenges and Prospects for Local Communities' Participation in the Decision-Making Processes* (PhD thesis, University of Dar es Salaam 2015) <http://localhost:8080/xmlui/handle/123456789/3380> accessed on 2nd April 2025

CSR practices.⁶¹ Therefore, despite the growth of CSR, stakeholders face challenges in developing, deciding, implementing, and evaluating CSR plans and projects.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

Different theories, including shareholder theory, the triple bottom line, social contract theory, and institutional theory, have been applied to explore the concept, nature, and enforcement of CSR and its associated challenges. The theory's interpretation and understanding of CSR, in turn, affect legal enforcement.⁶² The social contract theory outlines the relationship between society and businesses because they depend on each other. Hence, the social contract theory has led to understanding CSR as a social licence to operate.⁶³ Quid pro quo is the basis for interpreting CSR. Companies receive support and income from society and must contribute in return.⁶⁴ The triple-bottom-line theory promotes a balance among profit, people, and the planet. As a result, the triple-bottom-line approach has interpreted CSR as companies' responsibility for the impacts of their activities.⁶⁵ Hence, it urges companies to be responsible for the effects of their activities on society and the environment.

Shareholder theory posits that a company's primary focus is economic success rather than social success.⁶⁶ According to shareholder theory, companies should not allocate their resources to social undertakings unless they contribute to the growth of shareholders' wealth through profit maximisation.⁶⁷ Shareholder theory promotes the view that CSR is a strategy for enhancing the social capital of businesses.⁶⁸ Institutional theory focuses on

⁶¹ D Jamali and C Karam, 'Corporate Social Responsibility in Developing Countries as an Emerging Field of Study' (2018) 20(1) *International Journal of Management Reviews* 32-61. See also, A Chauhan, 'The Positive Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility: A Study of CSR in India' (2020) 11 *Indian Journal of Positive Psychology* 237.

⁶² O Swallehe, 'Implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility Initiatives for Tanzania Corporations and Not-for-Profit Organizations' in *Values and Corporate Responsibility: CSR and Sustainable Development* (2020) 259

⁶³ I R Kikwiye, "Relevance of multinationals' involvement in corporate social responsibility practices in Tanzania," *African Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, (2021) vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 247-268

⁶⁴ G Fooks, 'The Limits of Corporate Social Responsibility: Techniques of Neutralisation', (2013) *Stakeholder Management and Political CSR. Journal of Business Ethics*, 112(2), pp.283-299

⁶⁵ Burhan, A.M. and Kalinga, M. M. 'Perceptions of stakeholders in corporate social responsibility and irresponsibility in Tanzania' (2018) 8(9) *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*

⁶⁶ M Friedman, 'The Social Responsibility of Business Is to Increase Its Profits' (2007) in *Corporate Ethics and Corporate Governance* (Springer Berlin Heidelberg) 173.

⁶⁷ Ikasu, E.J. 'Examining the community perceptions on the Corporate Social Responsibilities of the mining companies in Kahama District, Tanzania' (2018) 2(7) *Economic Research* 12

⁶⁸ Isanzu, J.S. and Fengju, X. 'Impact of corporate social responsibility on firm's financial performance: the Tanzanian perspective' (2016) 7(1) *Journal on Innovation and Sustainability RISUS* 18.

the role of rules, norms, and regulations in shaping behaviour and practices.⁶⁹ This paper applies institutional theory to determine whether a standard definition of CSR is necessary for its effective legal enforcement. The relevance of institutional theory lies in the fact that this paper examines the relationship between the standard definition of CSR as a norm and legal enforcement.

3. UNDERSTANDING OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY IN TANZANIA

CSR is a multifaceted and dynamic concept with varied interpretations among stakeholders. This section examines how CSR is understood and interpreted, revealing divergent understandings and interpretations of CSR in Tanzania and their impact on enforcement challenges. It underscores the need for a standardised definition. A critical review of studies reveals four main categories of CSR understanding in Tanzania.

3.1 CSR is giving back to society

CSR is understood as a philanthropic activity because it is associated with providing donations and charitable services. The basis is that companies must do good to society as corporate citizens. Mader notes that CSR is widely understood as philanthropy and is thus typically referred to as charitable community support projects.⁷⁰ In addition, Ng'eni and others underscore that poverty reduction and sustainable development cannot be achieved solely through government actions.⁷¹ It requires help from all stakeholders, including business entities, through CSR initiatives and similar efforts to address poverty reduction and sustainable development, which are key national priorities in Tanzania.

While the understanding that CSR involves giving back to society is widespread in Tanzania, it contributes to the challenges CSR legal enforcement faces. First, insincere motives can arise when companies support highly beneficial causes to their image or profits rather than addressing more pressing societal needs and interests. Koehn and Ueng argue that companies use philanthropy as a form of moral window dressing.⁷² The study revealed that several firms with restated suspect earnings appear on top corporate giving lists or are among the most ethical firms. Second, unstructured, informal, and ad hoc discretionary philanthropic activities characterise understanding CSR as giving back to society. Amaeshi and others demonstrate that SMEs undertake their CSR practices to

⁶⁹ L L Melyoki, 'Corporate Social Responsibility Practices in the Extractive Sector in Tanzania: Is It a Transition from a Voluntary to Legislative Approach?' in *Social Entrepreneurship and Corporate Social Responsibility* (2020) 423

⁷⁰ K Mader, 'Corporate social responsibility in Tanzania: An overview' (Dar es Salaam: unpublished, 2012).

⁷¹ Ng'eni, F. B. and others, 'The role of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in community development in Tanzania' (2015) 5(6) *American Journal of Economics* 609.

⁷² Koehn, D. and Ueng, J. 'Is philanthropy being used by corporate wrongdoers to buy goodwill?' (2010) 14 *Journal of Management and Governance* 1

varying degrees across multiple spaces, including the workplace, marketplace, community, and ecological environment.⁷³

3.2 CSR is a social licence for business

Another understanding of CSR implies that companies obtain their licence to operate in society by contributing to the welfare and development of society. The social contract theory is the basis that outlines the relationship between society and businesses. This CSR interpretation operates based on a quid pro quo; companies receive support and income from society and must contribute to it in return. The rationale is that society and businesses depend on each other. Companies rely on society to operate profitably, while society relies on companies to enhance the welfare and development of their members. Msoka and Mbirigenda argue that CSR undertakings must mutually benefit corporations and local communities.⁷⁴ Swallehe highlights that although CSR initiatives in Tanzania are still in the early stages of development, there is significant room for improvement in how corporations implement and benefit from them.⁷⁵

Gillo and others reveal that most participants are aware of the CSR initiatives implemented by the North Mara Gold Mine and could articulate the company's responsibilities towards the local community.⁷⁶ Therefore, CSR is a mutual tool for both corporations and society. Kwikiye's study reveals that the CSR activities most preferred by multinationals and community members are almost identical, with a few exceptions that may be differences in the locations of stakeholders. However, the understanding that CSR is a social licence for business does not resolve the non-compliance faced by CSR enforcement because there is no legal foundation for such a quid pro quo relationship between society and companies. Studies show that there are possible divergences that may trigger the rejection of CSR projects and irrelevances in some cases.⁷⁷ Moreover, Fooks' study argues that CSR is a tool of stakeholder management aimed at mitigating the political impact of public health advocates by fragmenting political constituencies working towards evidence-based tobacco regulation.⁷⁸

⁷³ Amaeshi K. and others, 'Corporate social responsibility in SMEs: A shift from philanthropy to institutional works?' (2016) 138 *Journal of Business Ethics* 385

⁷⁴ Msoka, C.T. and Mbirigenda, S.K. 'Community Development through Corporate Social Responsibility: Some Issues from Selected Companies in Tanzania' (2015) 6(1) *Syllabus Review* 99.

⁷⁵ O Swallehe, 'Implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility Initiatives for Tanzania Corporations and Not-for-Profit Organizations' in *Values and Corporate Responsibility: CSR and Sustainable Development* (2020) 259

⁷⁶ I Gillo, et al., 'Corporate social responsibility practices: insights from North Mara gold mine, Tanzania' (2023) 12(6) *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science* 79

⁷⁷ I R Kikiye, "Relevance of multinationals' involvement in corporate social responsibility practices in Tanzania," *African Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, (2021) vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 247-268

⁷⁸ G Fooks, 'The Limits of Corporate Social Responsibility: Techniques of Neutralisation', (2013) *Stakeholder Management and Political CSR. Journal of Business Ethics*, 112(2), pp.283-299

3.3 CSR is the responsibility of companies for the impact of their activities

Another CSR interpretation denotes the responsibility of the companies for the impacts of their activities on society and the environment. Hence, companies should strike a balance between the profits they receive and the impacts they have on people and the environment. This CSR interpretation aligns with the triple bottom-line theory. The triple-bottom-line theory advocates that businesses balance profit, people, and the planet. Burhan and Kalinga contend that the responsibility for the impacts has two CSR components.⁷⁹ First, companies should produce socially desirable products and services as their central goal. Second, enterprises must provide responsible compensation if environmental or moral pollution is unavoidable. The interpretation of CSR as responsibility for impact represents a normative system with established standards, implementation mechanisms, and sanctions in Tanzania's extractive sector, as outlined in various legislation, including the Mining Act, the Tanzania Extractive Industries (Transparency and Accountability) Act, the Petroleum Act, and the Environmental Management Act. However, Melyoki highlights that the CSR legislative approach, the basis for CSR perception as a responsibility for impacts, stifles innovation in CSR, as companies set lower targets to avoid punishment.⁸⁰

3.4 CSR is a strategy for the social capital of businesses

"Social capital of business" refers to the networks, relationships, norms, and trust within and around a business organisation.⁸¹ CSR is a social capital because it enables companies to function effectively in society and strengthens them to collaborate with stakeholders, build goodwill, and maintain a positive reputation. The interpretation of CSR as social capital for business aligns with shareholder's theory. The shareholder theory argues that a company's primary responsibility is to benefit its shareholders.⁸² The company's management can use resources for social initiatives if doing so contributes to the shareholders' profits. A study by Isanzu and Fengju highlights that CSR has a positive influence on firm financial performance; hence, it suggests that the primary objective of

⁷⁹ Burhan, A.M. and Kalinga, M. M. 'Perceptions of stakeholders in corporate social responsibility and irresponsibility in Tanzania' (2018) 8(9) International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences

⁸⁰ Melyoki, L. 'Corporate Social Responsibility Practices in the Extractive Sector in Tanzania: Is It a Transition from a Voluntary to Legislative Approach?' in Social Entrepreneurship and Corporate Social Responsibility (2020) 423

⁸¹ J M Pennings and K Lee, 'Social Capital of Organization: Conceptualization, Level of Analysis, and Performance Implications' in S M Gabbay and R T-A Jaffe (eds), *Corporate Social Capital and Liability* (Springer US 1999) 43.

⁸² S T Homer and C M H D Gill, 'How Corporate Social Responsibility Is Described in Keywords: An Analysis of 144 CSR Definitions Across Seven Decades' (2022) Global Business Review 09721509221101141.

firms engaging in CSR is to enhance their economic performance and gain a competitive advantage.⁸³

Similarly, a study by Ikasu indicates that economic success is the most essential motivator for the company's CSR activities.⁸⁴ Understanding CSR as social capital for business contributes to the challenges facing CSR enforcement in Tanzania.⁸⁵ CSR is often employed as a branding or marketing strategy rather than a genuine commitment to sustainability, which is why it faces significant challenges in terms of environmental compliance, particularly in Tanzania's mining sector.⁸⁶ As a result, non-compliance with tax payments, environmental pollution, inadequate compensation for relocated communities, and low contribution to the national economy because CSR is only for the social capital of business and not otherwise.⁸⁷

4. LEGAL REGIME FOR CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

This section of the paper examines the legal framework governing CSR in Tanzania. The rationale behind this is to identify and address legal gaps that impact the enforcement of laws.

4.1 Overview of the legal regime

Tanzania does not have specific CSR legislation applicable to all economic sectors except for the extractive industries. The extractive industries have laws that mandate CSR implementation, especially in the mining and petroleum subsectors. The laws mandating CSR practice in the extractive sectors are the Mining Act, the Mining (Corporate Social Responsibility) Regulations, the Petroleum Act, and the Tanzania Extractive Industries (Transparency and Accountability) Act. The Mining Act requires the mineral rights holder to develop a credible CSR plan under Section 105. A similar obligation is in Section 222 of the Petroleum Act. The commitment to create a CSR plan is under the Mining (Corporate Social Responsibility) Regulations. The Tanzania Extractive Industries (Transparency and Accountability) Act requires extractive companies to submit reports

⁸³ Isanzu, J.S. and Fengju, X. 'Impact of corporate social responsibility on firm's financial performance: the Tanzanian perspective' (2016) 7(1) *Journal on Innovation and Sustainability* RISUS 18.

⁸⁴ Ikasu, E.J. 'Examining the community perceptions on the Corporate Social Responsibilities of the mining companies in Kahama District, Tanzania' (2018) 2(7) *Economic Research* 12

⁸⁵ Mganda, V.O. 'Challenges on the Practices of Corporate Social Responsibility in the Mining Sector in Tanzania: The Case Study of Bulyanhulu and Geita Gold Mine' (2016) 2(1) *Business Education Journal*.

⁸⁶ Mganda, V.O. 'Challenges on the Practices of Corporate Social Responsibility in the Mining Sector in Tanzania: The Case Study of Bulyanhulu and Geita Gold Mine' (2016) 2(1) *Business Education Journal*.

⁸⁷ Mtasigazya, P. 'Corporate social responsibility of the mining companies in Tanzania' (2021) (11) *Asia and Africa Today*, 46.

annually, as Section 15(1) outlines. Conversely, failure to submit CSR information and reports to the Extractive Committee is an offence under Section 15(3).

For non-extractive sectors, some laws address certain CSR aspects, such as consumer protection, employee interests, and environmental sustainability, although not in an expressly direct manner. The Fair Competition Act addresses consumer protection by prohibiting businesses from engaging in misleading or deceptive conduct in trade or commerce, as outlined in Section 15, and by protecting the rights of employees through relationships between companies, employees, and consumers, as detailed in Section 101. Section 183 of the Companies Act imposes an obligation on company directors to consider the interests of shareholders and employees. Section 6 of the Environmental Management Act accommodates the duty to protect the environment, and Section 81 imposes an obligation to undertake an environmental impact assessment.

4.2 Legal challenges facing the enforcement of CSR

First, there is the absence of a statutory definition of CSR. Despite having extractive and non-extractive laws catering to corporate social responsibility (CSR) in the country, none define CSR. The absence of such a definition opens Pandora's box to various interpretations among CSR stakeholders, given the diverse nature of the CSR concept. The open interpretations have led to inconsistent practices surrounding the idea of CSR across multiple sectors, including mining, tourism, agriculture, and others. As a result, CSR enforcement has not been achieving the intended objectives.

Second, the presence of ambiguous CSR-related terms. The phrase "credible CSR plan" under Section 105(1) of the Mining Act⁸⁸ is vague because it lacks clear criteria for determining a credible plan. The vagueness gives mineral rights holders and ministers discretion when developing a specific plan. The term 'comprehensive CSR plan' under Regulation 4(1) of the Mining (Corporate Social Responsibility) Regulations⁸⁹ is too broad to have specific enforcement measures when implementing the plan. Without definition, the use of 'interests' under Section 183(1) of the Companies Act is too broad for directors to rely on when discharging their duties. Section 15 of the Fair Competition Act prohibits misleading conduct but does not define the term. Consequently, CSR legal enforcement may be compromised due to the vagueness of the terms, as they allow for uncontrolled discretion in enforcement and lead to inconsistent interpretations.

Third, the narrow definition of stakeholders. The definition of host communities under Section 105(5) of the Mining Act encompasses the inhabitants of the local area of mining operations. However, the mining operations, by their nature, have more regional impacts. Hence, inhabitants of the nearby areas may be affected by the mining operations, but this

⁸⁸ Cap 123 R.E. 2019

⁸⁹ GN No. 409 of 2023

section does not include them. Additionally, Section 183(1) of the Companies Act⁹⁰ restricts directors from considering the interests of members and employees of the company; hence, the interests of consumers, suppliers, and local communities are not part of the obligation, creating a loophole where some CSR-critical issues may neither be addressed nor enforced under the said provision.

Fourth, there are unclear specifications of stakeholder roles. Section 105(2) of the Mining Act⁹¹ requires the mineral rights holder to consider the priorities of the host communities without stipulating who determines these priorities, as this can eventually impair CSR legal enforcement because it can lead to overlapping roles and conflicting situations between them. Section 183(1) of the Companies Act⁹² requires directors to consider the interests of company members and employees in their operations without specifying the actions directors must take to balance these interests when they conflict, hence challenging CSR legal enforcement. Section 15 of the Tanzania Extractive Industries (Transparency and Accountability) Act⁹³ grants mineral rights holders the authority to submit reports to the extractive committee but does not outline the committee's role in the CSR report. It raises the question of whether the committee has a role in enforcing CSR reporting. It undermines enforcement due to the lack of authority to address the CSR-submitted report.

Fifth, there is an absence of a precise mechanism for CSR enforcement. Section 15 of the Tanzania Extractive Industries (Transparency and Accountability) Act⁹⁴ does not outline the report's content or the mechanism for verifying the CSR reports and information submitted by extractive companies. Regulation 10 of the Mining (Corporate Social Responsibility) Regulations requires mineral rights holders and local authorities to consider social, environmental, economic, and cultural priorities in their plans. Enforcing provisions without consensus on CSR definitions and lacking clear metrics complicates this process. It results in subjective interpretations by mining companies and local authorities regarding the mining sites. Consequently, CSR regulators may struggle to evaluate compliance, potentially overlooking vital community priorities and undermining the purpose of CSR.

4.3 Implications for the legal enforcement of CSR

The absence of a standardised definition of CSR challenges assessing CSR performance. One of the vital items of CSR enforcement is assessing how and to what extent companies have been performing regarding CSR in different sectors. Difficulties in assessing CSR

⁹⁰ Supra

⁹¹ Cap 123 R.E. 2019

⁹² Act No. 12 of 2002

⁹³ Act No. 23 of 2015

⁹⁴ Act No. 23 of 2015

performance make CSR initiatives ineffective because stakeholders are blind spots to how far and effective CSR programmes are for companies, people, and the environment. Maliganya and others note that it is unclear how and to what extent CSR in the mining sector has contributed to development in areas of operations.⁹⁵ Additionally, Saad and others note that the lack of clarity regarding the scope and objectives of CSR makes it challenging to measure the impact and effectiveness of CSR initiatives.

Besides, CSR has been abused and misused due to the lack of a standardised definition of CSR. The absence of a common understanding of what CSR entails led to varied interpretations among companies implementing it in their business operations. Hence, as noted by Hoorn, such a limbo has 'allowed business enterprises to abuse and misuse it for their benefits rather than for meaningful social and environmental impacts.' Likewise, the REPOA report for 2020 highlights that CSR is often abused in Tanzania, as corporations operating in the country do not take it seriously. Therefore, due to a lack of common understanding of what constitutes CSR, a business enterprise may benefit from CSR abuses committed by others. How? When business enterprises reduce costs due to slave-like practices in their supply chain or fail to speak out in the face of abuse related to their operations, products, or services, despite having principled reasons to do so.⁹⁶

The lack of a standardised definition of CSR has led to inconsistent and selective compliance. Business enterprises have been complying with CSR selectively in the sense that CSR programmes may be in areas that are not priorities of the local communities. Moreover, the way and extent to which business enterprises have been performing CSR programmes are inconsistent. For instance, Sheehy's study highlights that major CSR programmes impact health, environment, community development, and education, particularly in areas where community priorities have on consumer protection and workforce development. As a result, CSR programmes are ineffective because companies are not fulfilling the expectations of local communities in their areas. Corroborating Mwelulila's study, it was concluded that CSR practices in Tanzania have been inconsistent across industries and regions.

Moreover, the absence of a common understanding of CSR in the country has created difficulties in drafting comprehensive and coherent CSR legislation. Legislators face a challenge in determining which stance to adopt when drafting legislation to create a conducive environment for CSR to operate smoothly and effectively. Tamvada inquired about what should constitute CSR and the nature of CSR regulation.⁹⁷ One of the findings

⁹⁵ Maliganya W. and others, 'Corporate Social Responsibility and the Challenges of the Regulatory Environment in the Tanzanian Mining Sector' in SK Msosa, S Mugova and C Mlambo (eds), *Corporate Social Responsibility in Developing Countries* (Springer 2023)

⁹⁶ United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 'The Corporate Responsibility to Respect Human Rights: An Interpretive Guide' (United Nations 2012)

⁹⁷ Tamvada, M. 'Corporate social responsibility and accountability: a new theoretical foundation for regulating CSR' (2020) 5 *Int J Corporate Soc Responsibility* 2

of Tamvada's study was that the absence of a standard definition of CSR has inhibited consistent CSR legislation in Tanzania and worldwide. Deductively, from this study, it may seem impossible to create comprehensive CSR legislation worldwide due to contextual variations and differing legal systems; however, based on the context of a country like Tanzania, it is possible to achieve a common understanding of what CSR entails. A government extend its role in providing adequate guidance and coordination needed to run the CSR ecosystem in the country in a constructive manner.

Generally, the lack of consensus on what CSR entails poses a significant challenge to enforcing CSR law in Tanzania. Why? The absence of a standardised definition of CSR leads to ambiguities, contributing to inconsistent and greenwashing CSR compliance. Another issue is that establishing clear benchmarks is challenging due to the lack of a standardised CSR definition. As a result, stakeholders are in a difficult position to monitor and evaluate CSR performance. Moreover, the absence of a standardised definition of CSR creates an undefined scope and requirements, as well as diverse stakeholder expectations; consequently, CSR practitioners face a dilemma in balancing the opposing interests of stakeholders when carrying out CSR programmes.

5. NECESSITY OF A STANDARD DEFINITION OF CSR FOR LEGAL ENFORCEMENT

The previous section indicated that Tanzania's current CSR legal framework reveals significant challenges. The specific laws subject to the analysis in this article were the Mining Act, the Tanzania Extractive Industries (Transparency and Accountability) Act, the Companies Act, the Fair Competition Act, and the Mining (Corporate Social Responsibility) Regulations. The challenges include the absence of a statutory definition of CSR in any legislation. Another issue is the presence of ambiguous CSR-related terms, such as 'credible CSR plans' and 'comprehensive CSR plans,' as well as the interests of employees, misleading or deceptive conduct without statutory explanation, and unclear specification of stakeholder roles. However, this section addresses the critical question of this study: Is a standard definition of CSR necessary for enforcement in Tanzania? It is essential because it aligns with the study's goal of analysing whether a standardised CSR definition can improve its legal enforcement. It demonstrates the relationship between the definition of CSR and its legal enforcement. This paper argues, in this section, that a standard definition of CSR is necessary for its legal enforcement in different ways hereby accounted for.

5.1 Clarity

The current legal framework includes vague terms, such as 'comprehensive CSR plan' under Regulation 4(1) of the Mining (Corporate Social Responsibility) Regulations and

'credible CSR plan' under Section 105(1) of the Mining Act. These ambiguous terms lead to varied interpretations by different CSR stakeholders, including mining companies, local government authorities, and local communities. Hence, companies may submit plans that differ significantly in quality and scope without a clear definition of CSR. Likewise, local government authorities may have different views on what constitutes a credible or comprehensive CSR plan to consider and approve before implementation. A standardised CSR definition would then clarify what constitutes CSR based on a consensus on what CSR is within Tanzania's context. Ultimately, the clarity presented here will ensure that all CSR stakeholders share a standard definition of CSR when developing, considering, approving, and enforcing a CSR plan. Therefore, stakeholders will clearly understand what CSR is about against which to evaluate CSR plans.

5.2 Discretionary powers

The absence of a clear definition of what the term 'interests' means, as provided under Section 183(1) of the Companies Act, opens a loophole for the company's directors to exercise their discretion when considering the interests of its members and employees during operations. As a result, the vagueness of interests can lead to decisions that do not genuinely reflect the interests of employees, even though these interests are essential components of CSR. As a result, the directors may dictate what interests to consider, which may differ from the actual interests of the employees. Henceforth, a standardised definition of CSR in the country can define specific interests that must be considered by the company's directors when affecting the company's day-to-day operations, including CSR aspects. As a result, the CSR standard definition can limit arbitrary decision-making by directors in these operations. For example, directors would be duty-bound to incorporate them into their CSR strategies if the definition included wages and safe and healthy interests.

5.3 Stakeholders' protection

Section 15 of the Fair Competition Act prohibits misleading or deceptive conduct but does not define what constitutes such conduct. The failure to define misleading or deceptive conduct creates difficulties in enforcing consumer protection. As a result, a standardised CSR definition can provide explicit guidance on consumer rights and protections based on defined deceptive or misleading conduct. Regulatory bodies, such as the Fair Competition Commission, can identify and address violations based on the statute's definition of deceptive or dishonest conduct. For example, if the definition specified that companies must provide transparent information about their products and services, it would empower consumers and regulators to hold businesses accountable for misleading practices, as there would be a common understanding of what CSR entails in terms of consumer protection issues.

5.4 Benchmarks and accountability

The absence of a common understanding of CSR in Tanzania has led to the lack of specific metrics against which monitoring and evaluation of CSR can determine whether CSR practices are effective or not when it comes to matters of the country's development goals. A standardised definition of CSR in the country promotes everyday awareness of CSR and the possibility of having standard metrics for benchmarking against best practices in CSR nationally and internationally. As a result, companies that share a common understanding of what CSR entails will consistently report on their activities. CSR stakeholders can evaluate companies based on performance against these metrics when a standardised CSR definition provides measurable indicators for measuring CSR impact.

5.5 Stakeholder engagement

Section 105(5) of the Mining Act recognises the host communities restrictively without regard to the regional impacts mining operations could have on people beyond where mining activities occur. In addition, Section 183(1) of the Companies Act requires directors to consider the interests of members and employees, excluding those of consumers and local communities. It is detrimental to effective CSR engagement during operations because the provisions are not inclusive due to the absence of consensus on what is understood by the term CSR within the country's context. Therefore, a clear and standardised definition of CSR will facilitate better engagement with stakeholders based on a common understanding of what stakeholders are and what we understand by CSR. Companies will likely involve multiple stakeholders rather than focusing solely on those mentioned in decision-making processes.

A standard definition of CSR emphasises stakeholder consultation. Stakeholder engagement is necessary for effective CSR enforcement. Although a standardised definition of CSR can help address significant legal gaps and enhance the effectiveness of CSR enforcement in Tanzania, it is necessary to acknowledge its limitations. A standardised definition of CSR cannot adequately account for the diverse cultural, social, and economic contexts. In addition, CSR enforcement can be affected by a lack of resources, expertise, or commitment to develop and execute meaningful CSR programmes beyond the standardised definition of CSR. If the legal framework lacks robust mechanisms for monitoring and enforcing compliance, the standard definition cannot remedy mischiefs of enforcement. Henceforth, this paper argues that although a standardised definition of CSR does not cure all challenges facing CSR legal enforcement in Tanzania, it lays a significant foundation for addressing the substantial legal gaps affecting CSR enforcement.

6. CONCLUSION

There is a growing awareness and adoption of CSR practices in Tanzania, throughout the region, and globally due to international trends, globalisation, and economic reforms in the 1980s. The growth encouraged the private sector to engage with socio-economic issues rather than relying solely on the government. However, no consensus remains on a standard definition of CSR. The lack of a shared understanding of CSR has led to misconceptions, misuse, and malpractice; CSR practices are inconsistent and ineffective. While CSR awareness and practices have risen in Tanzania, definitions of CSR vary significantly. The variations depend on the stakeholders and the sectoral context. Thus, these variations in CSR comprehension highlight CSR's complexities and dynamic nature in Tanzania and globally. The relationship between a standard definition of CSR and its legal enforcement lies in its absence, creating ambiguities that lead to inconsistent practices and instances of greenwashing within CSR compliance.

The CSR legislative framework has various gaps, such as no statutory definition, ambiguous terminologies, and no explicit guidance and roles. Hence, a standard definition of CSR can remedy legal gaps and enhance the effectiveness of CSR enforcement in Tanzania. It is also crucial to acknowledge its limitations, such as its failure to adequately consider diverse cultural, social, and economic contexts, alongside insufficient resources, expertise, or commitment to developing and implementing meaningful CSR programmes that exceed mere compliance with a standardised definition of CSR. The legal framework may have a limited impact on actual CSR practices if it does not include robust monitoring and enforcing compliance mechanisms. This paper proposes that a standard definition of CSR is the integration of social and environmental concerns into a company's business operations and interactions with stakeholders, assessed using specific performance indicators aligned with national development priorities. This study supports this definition as it provides a transparent and practical framework that can promote responsible and impactful business conduct.

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